

Two Kinds of Entropy in Quantum Mechanics?

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In a previous note (1) we suggested the existence of a quantum entropy associated with a free quantum particle with momentum p and wavefunction $\exp(ipx)$ due to the presence of a wavelength. The usual approach of using $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ in Shannon's entropy does not capture this entropy as it yields a constant for all p values. Thus we suggested using $|\cos(px)|/C$ where C is a normalization constant over half a wavelength. This value may be used in Shannon's entropy formula integrated over a half wavelength to give an entropy per crest. We then extended the idea to a quantum bound state.

In this note we wish to examine the relationship of this entropy to momentum i.e. energy flow. In (1) we noted that this entropy does not satisfy the first law of thermodynamics. Here we argue that it also does not satisfy the second law using ideas from refraction.

Finally we note that quantum thermodynamical calculations using temperature seem to ignore this entropy. In fact, these calculations ignore the usual $P(x)=W^*W$ or $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ Shannon's entropies for a pure state suggesting that only some "uncertainty" is included in typical entropy calculations while other uncertainty may apparently be ignored.

Classical Statistical Entropy

Classical statistical entropy is usually based on occupation of phase space (x,p) and was historically applied to gas particles. There seems to be no notion of entropy associated with a wavelength i.e. momentum in such a treatment. Shannon's entropy form $-\sum_i P(i) \ln[P(i)]$ where $P(i)$ is the probability for i emerged in classical statistical mechanics and seems to have been directly extended to quantum bound states with:

$$P(x) = W_n^*(x)W_n(x) \text{ and } P(p) = a_n^*(p)a_n(p) \text{ where } W_n(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a_n(p) \exp(ipx) \quad (1)$$

Thus two entropies, one momentum and one spatial, are applied to a bound state which has energy E_n (4). An electron in an atom, for example, may then jump from one E_n state to another by absorbing photons, but this uncertainty is then treated as being completely decoupled from the uncertainty (entropies) of the E_n states. Different E_n states have different momentum and spatial entropies, but this does not enter into a calculation of probabilities or entropy at all (2). As a result, the usual Maxwell-Boltzmann factor, albeit in terms of E_n i.e. $\exp(-E_n/T)$, appears in quantum calculations of standard entropy. This standard entropy is then understood to satisfy the first and second laws of thermodynamics.

Momentum Based Entropy

In (1) we suggested introducing a new quantum momentum (energy flow) entropy. This entropy captures the uncertainty of the wavelength of a particle or photon with wavelength λ where $p = \hbar/\lambda$. We use a half wavelength and use a probability of $|\cos(px)|/C$ where C

is a normalization constant. If one were to use $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$, this equals a constant for all p and so does not capture the wavelength entropy. One may note that this new momentum based entropy applies both to a particle with rest mass and a photon.

In (1) we noted that this momentum entropy does not satisfy the first law of thermodynamics because a particle with momentum p_1 may receive an impulse and change to p_2 . The change in kinetic energy is equivalent to the work done (as in a classical problem), but the momentum entropy differs.

To see how a probability distribution (used in the new momentum entropy) is linked to momentum (energy flow) one may consider the classical action written with $v=x/t$ i.e.

$$A = -Et+px \text{ (with } x \text{ and } t \text{ independent) This holds relativistically and nonrelativistically. ((2))$$

$$\text{In such a case: } -id/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx) \text{ ((3a)) and } id/dt \exp(-iEt) = E \exp(-iEt) \text{ ((3b))}$$

$-Et+px$ is a Lorentz invariant using the two 4-vectors (x,t) and (p,E) . Another invariant, however, is:

$$-EE + pp = m^2 c^4 \text{ ((4))}$$

Using ((3a)) and ((3b)) this leads to a wave equation i.e. the terms $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ are eigenfunctions of d/dx even though they are not eigenfunctions of d^2/dx^2 (only $\exp(ipx)$ is).

This notion that $-d^2/dx^2$ acting on a spatial function yields pp (momentum =energy flow) squared carries over into a quantum bound state problem where one has $W(x)$ (real function) (instead of $\cos(px)$ or $\sin(px)$) such that:

$$\text{KE average } \langle x \rangle = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{d^2 W/dx^2}{W} \text{ ((5)) where } 1/W(x) \text{ acts as a normalization}$$

Thus the probability distribution $W(x)$ behind the new quantum momentum based entropy is such that its second derivative d^2/dx^2 divided by $W(x)$ (normalization) yields the average or exact $\langle pp \rangle$ at x for a free particle as well as a bound quantum one.

In general $W(x)$, which is a real function, has crests/troughs of differing heights and widths unlike $\cos(px)$, but one may calculate the entropy per crest in the same manner.

One may note that like $\cos(px)$, as p (i.e. energy) increases, peaks become narrower. This same property holds for bound states (e.g. consider the quantum oscillator).

It may also be noted that energy does not need to change for the quantum momentum entropy to change. For example a free particle with momentum p (and a certain entropy) may pass through a single slit, double slit, triple slit etc and different patterns appear on a screen. The

momentum is unchanged (hence the kinetic energy), but the different patterns seem to suggest different entropies per crest.

Second Law of Thermodynamics

The second law of thermodynamics, which is linked to the idea of entropy increasing in spontaneous interactions, is a central idea of statistical mechanics. It seems, however, that this law does not hold for the momentum based quantum entropy. To see this consider a refraction scenario. One has two media and the speed of light is c/n_1 and c/n_2 in each respectively while momentum is (from (3))

$N_1 \hbar k_0$ in medium 1 and $n_2 \hbar k_0$ in medium 2 where $\hbar k_0$ is the momentum in a vacuum. ((6))

Thus a ray of light with momentum based entropy may change from having a small wavelength (i.e. low entropy) to a large wavelength (high entropy) spontaneously or vice versa. Both an increase or a decrease in quantum momentum based entropy occurs spontaneously. Thus the second law of thermodynamics does not seem to hold for this entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that there seem to be two entropies in quantum mechanics. The first seems to be based on classical statistical mechanics and considers energy levels and the jumping from one to another neglecting uncertainty within each energy level. This entropy is linked to the Maxwell-Boltzmann factor and leads to an entropy which satisfies the first and second laws of thermodynamics.

In the literature (4) it is acknowledged that there may be an entropy associated with a bound state E_n . In particular $P(x) = W_n^*(x)W_n(x)$ and $P(p) = \sum_n a_n(p)a_n(p)$ where $W_n(x) = \sum_p a_n(p) \exp(ipx)$ are used in Shannon's entropy to define spatial and momentum entropies for a bound state. These, however, do not seem to be used in calculations involving jumping among states E_n in a system with a temperature. This begs the question: What does one do with these pure state entropies?

We argue that using $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ in Shannon's entropy yields the same constant value for all free particle $\exp(ipx)$ s. This does not capture the entropy or uncertainty associated with a wavelength. Thus we suggested in (1) using $|\cos(px)|/C$ where C is a normalization constant over a half wavelength. We also noted that the first law of thermodynamics is not satisfied by this entropy. In this note we show that the second law of thermodynamics is not satisfied. We also show the link between momentum (energy flow) squared and the second derivative d^2/dx^2 of the new probability function needed to calculate the new momentum quantum entropy.

References

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